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Multiband imaging of a sandstone object with blue pigment

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Abbreviations

IR	Infrared (ca. 700–1100 nm)
IRR	Infrared reflectance
IRRFC	Infrared-reflected false-colour
MBI	Multiband imaging
UV	Ultraviolet (ca. 200–400 nm)
UVL	Ultraviolet luminescence
UVR	Ultraviolet reflectance
UVRFC	Ultraviolet-reflected false-colour
VIL	Visible-induced luminescence
VIS	Visible (ca. 400–700 nm)

Objects description

Sandstone with blue pigment

Purpose

Multiband imaging (VIS, IRR, UVL, UVR, IRRFC, VIL) was performed for documentation and to visualize the blue pigment particles.

Comments on set-up

All images were captured with the object placed horizontally with the camera mounted above. The object was placed on a black paper background and supported to keep the area with blue pigment flat. The camera was positioned c. 50cm above the object and two light sources were placed on opposite sides with approximately a 45-degree angle towards the object.

Comments on standardisation and post processing

The Heritage Laboratory follow the guidelines for multiband imaging as presented in the user manual that was developed by the British Museum during the EU-funded CHARISMA project¹. The manual details practices to improve the reproducibility of the method between users and institutions, including the use of specific standards. For post processing Nip2 is a graphical interface for the image processing system VIPS that is open-source and can be downloaded free of charge². Nip2 has many features; for example, it can utilize standards to colour calibrate and correct for spatial inhomogeneities of the light source. The processing and use of Nip2 is described in detail in the manual. Every object and on-site photography setup provide different circumstances and challenges, therefore some variation in set-up between sessions may occur.

Image types

Image	Radiation source	Filter	General purpose
VIS	VIS (flash)	VIS	Standard image.
IRR	IR (flash)	IR	IR reflection upon illumination by IR radiation. Useful to study underdrawings in paintings. Many materials such as organic dyes and binders become transparent under these conditions.
UVL	UV	VIS	Luminescence in the VIS region upon illumination by UV radiation. Useful to visualize organic binders and dyes. Some inorganic materials also have luminescent properties, e.g. zinc oxide.
UVR	UV	UV	UV reflection upon illumination by UV radiation. Useful to visualize surface structure, coatings and varnishes.
IRRFC			In IRRFC the red channel from IRR is combined with the red and green channel from the VIS image. Some pigments have characteristic colour changes.
UVRFC			In UVRFC the blue channel from UVR is combined with the green and blue channel from the VIS image. Some pigments have characteristic colour changes.
VIL	VIS (LED)	IR	For visualisation of Egyptian blue, Han blue and Cd-pigment

Equipment

Camera	Nikon D850 (modified to full spectrum, UV-IR blocking filter removed)
Lens	Nikon AF NIKKOR 105 mm
Filters	CHSOS Robertina filters for VIS, UV and IR, B+W 093 for IR
Light sources	Godox speedlight V860ii for VIS and IRR CHOS Fabrizio UV-light for UVL and UVR Godox LED1000 II for VIL
Software	Adobe Photoshop, Adobe Camera Raw, Adobe Bridge, Nip2 with Bm-workspace
Standards	Calibrite Classic Mini McBeth color chart Spectralon© reflectance standards; 99 %

Radiation sources

Irradiance profile of Nikon Speedlight V860ii measured at 100 cm distance with an Ocean Optics Flame spectrometer.

Godox LED1000 II measured at 100 cm distance with an Ocean Optics Flame spectrometer.

CHSOS Fabrizio UV-light measured at 100 cm distance with an Ocean Optics Flame spectrometer.

Raw data

Tif and jpg images are stored on the Swedish National Heritage Boards raw database Lida (L:) and available upon request.

References

1. Dyer, J., Verri, G. & Cupitt, J., 'Multispectral Imaging in Reflectance and Photo-induced Luminescence modes: a User Manual', 2013, Web publication/site, European CHARISMA Project, Online.
2. GitHub - BritishMuseum/bm-charisma: A nip2 workspace for technical imaging <https://github.com/BritishMuseum/bm-charisma> (2023-03-24)

Images and results

Results from MBI are indicative and should always be accompanied by analytical methods. MBI was performed on the part of the object that contain blue pigment. The area with pigment particles measures around 2x2cm. The expected results from blue pigments containing copper are summarized in Table 1. The main differences between azurite and Egyptian blue should be seen in IRRFC and VIL. Interference from the substrate (sandstone) is evident in these images, a heterogenous background makes conclusions difficult. The imaged blue pigment did not show any visible-induced luminescence (VIL), hence azurite is the most likely conclusion that can be drawn by MBI. MBI also indicate that the blue pigment is the same material and not a mixture as no variations can be seen in the image response from the pigment. In the UVL image glue is visible.

Table 1. Expected MBI results from azurite and Egyptian blue (Cu-containing blue pigments)

Pigment	VIS	IRR	IRRFC	VIL	UVR	UVL
Azurite	Blue	Dark	Purple	-	Dark	-
Egyptian blue	Blue	Dark/Transp	Red	Bright	Dark	-

VIS

IRR

IRR False colour

UVL

UVR

VIS (for VIL)

VIL

Azurite references

A set of azurite references demonstrate the expected response in MBI. Azurite ground to different particle size in two different binders (rabbit glue and linseed oil), on a white (chalk) and a black (ivory black) background. A mineral sample (USA) is also included. All references were available from the Heritage Laboratory reference collection.

White background (Chalk + glue) Black background (Ivory black + glue)

VIS

IRR

IRRF C

UVR